

“SARDAR PATEL: AN ICON OF THE NATIONAL INTEGRATION OF BHARAT”

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Abstract: *Vallabhbhai Patel is popularly known as ‘Sardar’ Patel, the ‘Iron Man of Bharat’, the ‘Modern Ashoka’ and the ‘Bismarck of Bharat’. He was one of the most towering and revered figures in the history of Bharat who had played a pivotal role in making Bharat an independent, unified and modern nation-state. After the departure of the British from Bharat in the mid-twentieth century, he effectively and successfully merged 565 fragmented Princely States into the ‘Union of Bharat’ within a short span of time without any bloodshed with his sharp diplomatic strategies and political foresightedness, ensuring territorial integrity and national unity. In fact, it was not a small task, rather a gigantic one of amalgamating the diverse Princely States into a single entity. Because during the time of unification mainly three states (Hyderabad, Junagarh and Jammu and Kashmir) posed the biggest challenges. The present paper seeks to examine and evaluate the significant contributions of Sardar Patel in the integration of the Princely States into the ‘Union of Bharat’ in the aftermath of Independence from the British colonial rule. The paper discusses the developments in the process of national unification in the subsequent years after the demise of Sardar Patel. Further, the study concludes by analyzing the recent developments in line with the Sardar Patel’s vision by the Modi Government.*

Keywords: Sardar Patel, National Integration, Fragmented Princely States, Union of Bharat, Recent Developments

1.INTRODUCTION:

The structure of the ‘strong and unified Bharat’ that we see today is the result of the indomitable spirit, unwavering determination, perseverance and relentless efforts of the Bharat Ratna Vallabhbhai Patel. He is popularly known as ‘Sardar’ Patel, the ‘Iron Man of Bharat’, the ‘Modern Ashoka’ and the ‘Bismarck of Bharat’. He was a key figure in Bharat’s struggle for freedom and the architect of its unification. His remarkable role in making Bharat an independent, unified and modern nation-state can never be forgotten.

Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel, the sixth child to Jhaverbhai and Ladbai, born on 31st October 1875 in a middle-class farmer’s family in Nadiad Gujarat. His father was a patriotic farmer who participated in the 1857 uprising and his mother was a deeply religious and hard-working woman. Patel passed his matriculation in 1897 from Nadiad High School. Then he moved to England for higher studies in 1910 and completed his LL. B from the Middle Temple in 1912.

Patel was one of the most towering and revered figures in the history of Bharat. He was a successful lawyer, a senior leader and the 49th President of the Indian National Congress (INC), a big follower of Mahatma Gandhi and a founding father of the Republic of Bharat. After independence, Sardar Patel served as Bharat’s first Deputy Prime Minister and Home Minister. He had also significant role as the Chairman of the Committees for Fundamental Rights, Minorities, Tribal and Excluded Areas and Provincial Constitution and many provisions such as the Right to Private Property, Privy Purses for the rulers of the Princely States and Constitutional guarantees for the Civil Servants.

2.PATEL’S ROLE AS A FREEDOM FIGHTER:

The major turning point in Patel’s life took place after he met Mahatma Gandhi during the Kheda Satyagraha in 1918. Gandhi chose Patel as his deputy commander to lead the satyagraha. Patel led the peasants in refusing to pay taxes due to famine-induced hardships. It was the first major success of Patel against the British colonialism. After this he involved increasingly in the freedom fight against the British. Again in 1928, another peasant movement called the Bardoli Satyagraha was led by him against the unjust tax hikes, earning him the title ‘Sardar’ meaning a leader of the masses. He was greatly influenced by the achievements of Mahatma Gandhi. After these two peasant movements he emerged a popular leader in the national freedom struggle. During this time,

he was also attracted by the principles of Mahatma Gandhi like truth, non-violence, spirituality, discipline, moral strength and he supported and participated in all the three national movements (Non-Cooperation Movement, Civil Disobedience Movement and Quit India Movement) launched by Gandhiji against the British Colonial Rule. For the cause of national struggle for independence he was arrested and jailed several times.

3.SARDAR PATEL AS THE UNIFIER OF BHARAT:

After the departure of the British from Bharat in the mid- twentieth century, there were two sets of territories like territory of British India and Princely States. The dawn of the newly independent nation was full of many complexities and struggling for its unification and it was Sardar Patel the great son of Bharat who effectively and successfully merged 565 fragmented Princely States into the 'Union of Bharat' within a short span of time without any bloodshed with his sharp diplomatic strategies, negotiating skills, political foresightedness and military actions, ensuring territorial integrity and national unity. Hence, in this regard, Sardar Patel is compared to Otto Von Bismarck of Germany who had done the same this in his country during 1860s. It was nearly 2000 years after the Emperor Ashoka the great that such a unification took place in Bharat subcontinent. So, Patel is called Modern Ashoka and architect of modern Bharat. In fact, it was not a small task, rather a gigantic one of amalgamating the diverse Princely States into a single entity. Because during the time of unification mainly three states like Hyderabad, Junagarh and Jammu and Kashmir posed the biggest challenges, choosing to remain independent after partition. During this time Nizam, Nawab and Raja Hari Singh were the rulers of Hyderabad, Junagarh and Jammu and Kashmir respectively. However, in due course of time, these three states were merged with the Union of Bharat through different means like Hyderabad through a military action (Operation Polo on 17th September 1948), Junagarh through a landmark plebiscite (February 1948) and Jammu and Kashmir through the instrument of accession (worked out between October 1947 and 26th November 1949). In fact, Sardar Patel carried three-fold-process of assimilation, centralization and unification of states. The states were first integrated to form a union and then that union was amalgamated with the Union of Bharat. In addition, Sardar Patel had another important contribution to the nation i.e. the creation of All India Services. He had envisioned the All-India Services as the 'Steel Frame of Bharat', thus further safeguarding the national unity and integrity. Moreover, Sardar Patel is regarded as the 'Iron Man of Bharat' as the way he brought about and

maintained the internal stability as the union Home Minister in a newly partitioned and fragmented nation.

Sardar Patel died on 15th December 1950 after a massive heart attack at Birla House in Bombay, now in Maharashtra, leaving behind an indelible legacy as the 'Icon of the National Integration of India'. Following the sad demise of Patel tributes poured globally, with the Independent Bharat 's first Prime Minister Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru described him as a "tower of strength and a "builder of modern India". Sardar Patel was conferred the 'Bharat Ratna Award' posthumously in 1991.

4.NATIONAL UNIFICATION AFTER PATEL:

After the demise of Sardar Patel, the process of national unification did not stop, rather it continued in the subsequent years. After prolonged negotiations with the French authorities in 1954 the territory of Pondicherry was handed over to Bharat. In 1956 the States Reorganization Act was enacted and it was a landmark towards the national unification. The Act repealed the four categories of states (A, B, C and D) as provided under the original Constitution and classified these states into only two categories like the States and the Union Territories. The Act provided for the creation of 14 states and 6 Union Territories. In 1961, Indian Army marched into Goa which was under the control of Portuguese. With the Operation Vijay Goa, Daman and Diu were annexed into the Union of Bharat and made into a Union Territory. Later in 1987 Goa was separated splitting the Union Territory and elevated to the status of a state. In 1975 , Sikkim was annexed into the Union of Bharat , its Monarchy rule was abolished and it became a state by the 36th Constitutional Amendment Act of 1975.

5.RECENT DEVELOPMENTS:

When Narendra Modi became the Prime Minister in 2014, his government decided to honor the great son of Bharat Sardar Patel. Accordingly, "Rashtriya Ekta Divas" (National Unity Day) is observed each year in Bharat on 31st October -Patel's birth anniversary since 2014.Next year in 2015, during the "Rashtriya Ekta Divas", the idea of "Ek Bharat Shreshtha Bharat" was mooted by the Prime Minister Modi. The PM Modi said that Bharat's cultural diversity is a joy that should be celebrated mutually amongst the people of different States as well as Union Territories. In fact, the understating of different cultures, traditions and practices of the States as well as Union Territories will further strengthen the unity and integrity of Bharat.

The Hon'ble Prime Minister Narendra Modi dedicated the 'Statue of Unity' - statue of Sardar Patel (world's tallest statue with a height of 182metres, 597 feet, situated on the bank of the Narmada River, near Kevadia, Gujarat) to the nation on the 143rd birth anniversary of Patel in 2k18, thus highlighting the devotion and remarkable and incomparable contributions of Sardar Patel' in making Bharat an independent, unified and modern nation-state. The 'Statue of Unity' will continue to remind and inspire the generations to come the courage, devotion, dedication and capability that Sardar Patel has had.

Today, Modi Government's current policies like the "Make in India" and "Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan" (Self-reliant Bharat Campaign) are the reflections of the vision of Sardar Patel. Moreover, Modi Government's spirit of 'Sabka Sath, Sabka Vikas, Sabka Vishwas and Sabka Prayas' is also the reflection of Patel's vision.

It is said that if the then Prime Minister Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru had not intervened in the matter of merging the Princely State of Jammu and Kashmir ruled by Maharaja Hari Singh, then the matter would have been resolved by Sardar Patel and it would have not become a major problem for the nation until 2k19. However, the matter has been resolved in August 2k19 when Narendra Modi Government took a very strong and visionary decision to abrogate Article 370 of the Constitution of Bharat (the temporary, transitional and Special Status of erstwhile state of Jammu and Kashmir). Jammu & Kashmir was split into Union Territory of Jammu and Kashmir and Union Territory of Ladakh. In fact, this completed the true unification of Bharat as Patel had envisioned after the partition when the nation was struggling for its geography of unity and integrity.

6. CONCLUSION:

In view of the aforesaid facts, it can be concluded that due to Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel' remarkable contributions Bharat is today a strong, unified and modern nation. The present Union Government under the leadership the Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi is strongly following the legacy of Sardar Patel for the cause of national unity and integrity. It is evident from so many steps of the government like the celebration of "Rashtriya Ekta Divas", "Statue of Unity", "Ek Bharat Shreshtha Bharat", "Make in India", "Atmanirbhar Bharat" and abrogation of Article 370. Modi Government's spirit of 'Sabka Sath, Sabka Vikas, Sabka Vishwas and Sabka Prayas' also reflects Patel's legacy. Above all, Sardar Patel is the real Icon of the National Integration of Bharat.

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